

Design and Fabrication of Die for Powder metallurgy compaction

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Abstract

Die design is one of the most crucial steps in powder metallurgy since the finished component's properties are directly impacted by the form and characteristics of the die. Before manufacture, there are a number of procedures and considerations involved in die design. The aim of this work is to develop and create a die for the powder metallurgy process. Design considerations, 3D models, and die fabrication procedures are all included. In this work, a die that will be used to create circular specimens is designed and made. The die and the punch both are made of AISI D2 steel.

Keywords: Powder Metallurgy, Die design, Fabrication;

1.0 Introduction

In powder metallurgy (PM), compacted metal powders are heated to just below their melting temperatures in order to create metal components. In other terms, PM is a metal Processing method that uses powdered metal to produce near-net parts. The majority of alloys and composites are developed using the rapidly expanding method powder metallurgy (PM). It involves three primary steps: combining powdered ingredients, compressing them into the appropriate shape, and heating the compressed mixture to bind the substance [1]. Although the technology has been used for more than a century, it has only recently gained widespread acceptance as a superior method of creating high-quality parts for a range of significant applications. This success can be attributed to the advantages the technique has over conventional metal forming processes like forging and metal casting, including better material utilization, increased shape complexity, and improved near-net-shape dimensional control. Powder metallurgy is a recognised green technology which promote sustainability[x]. The ability to create components without them breaking down or degrading is another benefit of the PM process. Another advantage of the PM process is that the components can be manufactured without decomposing or dissolving the material by avoiding the changes in material properties in the solid-liquid phase [2]. Al-Qureshi et.al [3] achieved full densification by several routes and often involves the simultaneous application of stress and temperature to close residual pores. This is accomplished through extrusion or cold and hot forging methods. Hofmann & Bowen [4] research have investigated the cold forming of ferrous and nonferrous powder preforms and have reported the merits of the process such as good surface finish, higher accuracy, and superior strength due to work hardening and geometric hardening. Some disadvantages of hot forging include the oxidation and decarburization of the surfaces of billets, a high rate of wear, poor dimensional accuracy and surface cleaning, and the development of thermal tensions.

Numerous researchers have examined powder kinds, characterisation, manufacturing, alloying, and mixing for the P/M steels. Jhavar et.al and Mauricio Barrera et.al [5-6] conclude that low-alloy P/M steels containing Cr, Mo, Si, Ferro Si, Cu and Mn, manufactured from elemental powders are suitable for precision parts of automotive engines and transmissions. As a result, the current research effort takes into account mixed elemental metal powders including Cr, Ni, and Mo that are exposed to a single pressing and sintering operation. Sintered powder materials behave differently during cold and hot forging in terms of plastic deformation and densification than conventional materials. Therefore, in-depth research is necessary to understand the plastic deformation of the sintered Powder Metallurgy steels. Strengthening of sintered P/M low alloy steels can be achieved through densification, alloying and heat treatment [7-8]. Cracks in powder metallurgy (P/M) components primarily until the sintering has occurred, the root cause is most likely the poor inter-particle bonding obtained prior to the sintering [9-12]. The simplest type of powder compaction is uniaxial compaction. The fluctuation in pressed density was one of this type's drawbacks. The main cause of this limitation is the die-wall particle and particle-particle friction, which ultimately cause the micro-crack on the surface of green compact [12]. Originate from the compaction prior to the sintering. Although the cracks may not become evident.

Since we'll be using the word "die" in our work, it might be a good idea to explain what it means. It came out in two different ways. When used in a broad sense, it refers to a press tool as a whole, including all of its individual parts. When used more specifically, it describes the part that is machined to take the blank, as opposed to the part known as the punch, which is its opposing element. The compact shape, density, powder mix composition, compaction and radial pressure, part number, and tool materials are the primary data required to construct a metal powder compaction die. The design objectives are: insert and ring diameters, occasionally ring count and interference or interferences. The limitations include the absence of tensile stresses on the insert, the absence of any chance of relative motion at part ejection, the avoidance of any unintended modification of material microstructures, and maximum stresses that are always within the permissible limits. The design is typically based on engineering expertise, business expertise, approximations of analytical calculations, and cost concerns. The primary goal of this work is to apply numerical techniques to identify the die design parameters for compacting powder. Investigations have been done on warm compaction as well as room temperature.

Applied numerical algorithms. To make the dies simpler to assemble than the five-piece dies previously in use, two-piece designs were taken into consideration. The two points of tension in the die cavity's inner corner and the distortion of the cavity wall caused by the interference fit of the two components and the pressure put on the die during the compaction process were the two areas of concern. Stresses in a successful die design would be lower than the material's yield stress. The compaction force, cavity size, and outside radius are some of the design elements that were examined.

2.0 DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF DIE FOR POWDER COMPACTION

2.1 Design of Die:

3D model of the die and punch set with were prepared using AutoCAD (3D Modelling) software. The sample models of lower punch(Length =10 mm, Diameter =30 mm, Tail length =20 mm Tail Diameter =50 mm), die(Length = 80 mm, Outer Diameter =50 mm Inner Diameter = 10 mm) punch(Length = 45 mm, Diameter =10 mm Holding length =10 mm, Holding Diameter =25 mm), release cap(outer dia =50mm, inner dia =15mm, length=10mm) and assembled view are shown in figures 1(a), 1(b), 1(c), 1(d) and 1(e) respectively. The relief given in the punch is usually given to reduce the area of contact between punch and wall of die cavity and thus minimizing friction and wear of both punch and die wall.

Fig. 1(a)
Lower punch

Fig. 1(b)
Die

Fig. 1 (c)
Upper Punch

Fig. 1(d)
Release Cap

Fig. 1 (e)
Assembly view

2.2 Material used

The die was made of AISI D2 tool steel, which was also used for the upper punch, lower punch, and release cap. The die dimensions were chosen in accordance with ASTM (American Society for Testing and Materials) standards.

The following table shows the chemical composition of D2 tool steels.

Element	C	Mn	Si	Co	Cr	Mo	V	P	Ni	Cu	S
Content (%)	1.4-1.6	0.6	0.6	1.0	11-13	0.7-1.2	1.1	0.03	0.3	0.25	0.03

- Source AZO Materials

Table: 1 chemical composition of D2 tool steels.

Mechanical Properties

The mechanical properties of D2 steels are tabulated below. (Source AZO Materials)

Mechanical Properties	Metric	Imperial
Knop Hardness	769	769
Rockwell C Hardness,	62	62
Vickers Hardness,	748	748
Poisson's ratio	0.27-0.30	0.27-0.30
Elastic modulus	190-210 GPa	27557-30457 Ksi

D2 steel is an air hardening, high-carbon, high-chromium tool steel. It has high wear and abrasion resistant properties. It is heat treatable and will offer a hardness in the range 55-62 HRC, and is machinable in the annealed condition. D2 steel shows little distortion on correct hardening. D2 steel's high chromium content gives it mild corrosion resisting properties in the hardened condition.

2.3 Die calculation

$$\text{Area, } A = \pi r^2 = 3.14 \times 5 \times 5 = 78.53 \text{ mm}^2$$

Assuming a load of 200000 N,

Stress, $\sigma = \text{Load/Area} = 200000 / 78.53 = 2546.79 \text{ MPa}$. The ultimate yield strength and ultimate tensile strength of D2 tool steel are 780 MPa and 210 MPa respectively. So, the die tends to withstand the given load with ease.

Lame's Equation for calculating the thickness of thick cylindrical shells:

Thickness

$$t = \frac{d}{2} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\sigma + p}{\sigma - p}} - 1 \right)$$

Where, d = internal diameter of shell (mm)

P = internal pressure (MPa or N/mm²)

σ = tangential stress (MPa or N/mm²)

Working Stress = (S/Factor of safety) (where S = ultimate tensile stress)

We design the thick cylindrical shells to be safe against tangential stress, since for thick cylindrical shells,

Tangential Stress > Longitudinal Stress > Radial Stress

3.0 FABRICATION OF DIE

3.1 Turning

The general process of turning involves rotating a part while a single-point cutting tool is moved parallel to the axis of rotation [13]. Turning is a form of machining and a material removal process, which is used to create rotational parts by cutting away unwanted material

Fig2: 3D view and image of Turning operation

3.2 Facing

Facing is the process of removing metal from the end of a work piece to produce a flat surface.

Fig3: Image of facing operation in lathe machine

3.3 Drilling

A drill bit is used in the cutting process of drilling to create a hole in solid materials. A multipoint, end-cutting tool is a drill bit. The work piece is compressed and rotated to create a cut, creating chips at the cutting edge. While rotating at speeds ranging from hundreds to thousands of revolutions per minute, the bit is forced against the work piece. By pressing the cutting edge against the work piece, this prevents chips from exiting the hole as it is being drilled.

Fig4: Image of Drilling Operation in lathe machine

3.4 Lapping

Lapping in machining is the process of sizing and polishing small diameter holes that have already undergone hardening by removing very little material with the use of a lapping paste. We employed Boron Carbide lapping paste, a high-performance abrasive with diamond-like hardness and chemical resistance.

Fig5: Surface finish operation

3.5 Heat Treatment

A range of industrial and metalworking operations known as heat treatment are used to change a material's physical, and occasionally chemical, qualities. Heat treatment uses heating or cooling typically to very high temperatures—to harden or soften materials in order to obtain a desired outcome. Annealing, case hardening, precipitation strengthening, tempering, and quenching are all types of heat treatment. The die was bathed in oil for 20 minutes, then hardened at 900°C. At 200°C, the tempering was carried out for an average of 45 minutes per inch of die thickness. After heat treatment, the die material had a hardness of 62 HRC.

CONCLUSION:

An impact die for the powder metallurgy process was designed and constructed in this work. Failures included poor powder material compaction and the upper and lower punches bending during load application, which were overcome. In comparison to die made from other materials, the die was manufactured from higher quality material (AISI D2), which has superior mechanical and thermal characteristics.

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